

Theory of Socio-Humanism by Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev And Its Ecological, Spiritual, Moral, Creative Society Against the Consumer Society of the Global Neoliberal Capitalism of the Global Masonic Mafia-Driven Elite and its Deep Management

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ABSTRACT: Lord Prof. PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev developed 2006 Theory of socio-humanism by developing the creation of a new human society with a new political, economic, social, health, educational, environmental system, a new system of control of political and other decisions - direct democracy, creating a system of direct democracy in the judiciary, in the legislative system, Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova established in 2006. "Theory of degree of justice / injustice /" as well as "Theory of the degree of democracy" based on their practice in court, prosecution, state and especially the practice of Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev as a judge with decades of experience as such as a civil and a criminal judge. Prof. Momchil Dobrev co-founded 2003 Theory of Corruption and Theory of the Mafia and Theory and Practice of Mafia, which contribute to clearing the Theory of the Degree of Justice / Injustice.

KEYWORDS: Socio-humanism, Justice, mafia, corruption, theory,

1. INTRODUCTION

Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Lady Prof. Mariola Garibova developed in 2006. Theory of socio-humanism, which theory represents a social system of political, social, economic, humanistic management of society that opposes the modern capitalism of the global Masonic mafia elite and its deep rule and deep state.

The theory of socio-humanism is a critique of modern global neoliberal capitalism and also give a solution and its structure of government both in each country and at the international level and provides a solution for creating a new social system - more harmonious and humanistic and centered on man's ecological system. in which he lives.

Theory of socio-humanism puts new principles the whole government of a country in accordance with the ecological system, and the creative, creative qualities of each person, a new economic system, a new social system, a new ecological system related to man, a new political system of direct democracy and governance through referendums.

Theory of socio-humanism puts the government on a new principled basis, both the political governance of a country in the modern world and the new economic governance in a country based on the new principled basis, the new governance in the judiciary, the new governance in the ecological system, the social system, the system of education, health care, climate and ecology, culture and a system of direct control of the whole system - through a system of direct democracy.

In the year 2001 Lord Prof. Momtchil DObrev developed the Theory of the mafia and Theory of corruption . All the both theories has been developed by analyzing of the mafia and the corruption all over the wprld. In Bulgaria, germany, European Union, and other countires.

Lord Prof. PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev developed 2006 "Theory of degree of justice / injustice /" based on their practice in court, prosecution, state and especially the practice of Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev as a judge with decades of experience as such as a civil and criminal judge . Prof. Momchil Dobrev co-founded 2003 Theory of Corruption and Theory of the Mafia and Theory and Practice of Mafia, which contribute to clearing the Theory of the Degree of Justice / Injustice.

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In the year 2010 Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed the 'Theory of Mafiotismus' as a new type of government oriented solely in the private interests of individuals and private institutions.

In this article we define the basic principles of the SOCIETY created on the basis of the Theory of Socio-Humanism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobрева and the differences of this society with the current global neoliberal capitalist society ruled by the global Masonic mafia elite and its deep and a deep state.

1.1 Introduce the Problem

The problem of the crisis of the current capitalist global neoliberal society is enormous and leads to the real demise of our civilization.

Theory of socio-humanism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobрева create a system for a new society with new principles of social, political, economic, social, ecological life of the countries on the planet Earth. This system of a new society will provide a real rest of civilization and the preservation of this civilization. This system completely replaces the capitalist system which is the real cause of the crises of society, the creation of inequalities, the robbery of entire countries, peoples, consumers of a global Masonic mafia elite that governs countries all over the world through a deep government and a deep state.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

Research methods of analysis, verification, critique of the current society and a capitalist global neoliberal system that works only for the benefit of the global Masonic mafia elite.

- Analysis of democracies in the world
- Analysis of political systems
- Analysis of the economic system in the world
- Analysis of the laws of a country.
- Analysis of all authorities in a country - judicial, legislative, executive
- Analysis of the implementation of the laws of a country
- Analysis of managed public resources
- Analysis of the existence of corruption and mafia in the judiciary, in the state system.
- Analysis of the work of the prosecutor's office as a guarantor of the existence and development of mafia.
- Analysis of the judiciary - laws, judges, selection of judges, development of judges, violations of judges, disciplinary and other liability of judges, prosecutors, investigators.

3. THE REALITY IN THE CAPITALIST GLOBAL NEOLIBERAL SOCIETY CURRENTLY RULED BY THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA ELITE AND ITS DEEP MANAGEMENT AND DEEP STATE

The current conditions on the planet are not good.

People suffer deprivation, restrictions, poverty, hunger, disease, drinking water problems, wars, terrorism, devastation, climate change, refugees, increased mortality, increased demographic crisis, low health care, poor and inhumane medicine, abandoned children, child labor, use of children for organs, misery, low pay of workers.

At the same time, high taxes, high utility prices, high prices for electricity, water, energy,

Capitalist class society stratifies class society.

There are different classes such as - working poor, unemployed poor, poor, middle class, elite - rich elite.

The unemployed poor are those who cannot find a job, do not have a home, and have enough income to cover their expenses.

They cannot pay for their basic needs either.

Capitalism created and ruled by the global Masonic mafia elite cannot stimulate the unemployed poor, the working poor, they cannot develop. Capitalism, ruled by the global Masonic mafia elite, is the driving force of the ego and of capital, of money, of profit.

The goal is profit, income as high as possible, which is not based on any morality, honor, dignity, ethics, value system.

The fear of survival leads the working and unemployed poor to greed, unscrupulousness, striving for dominance, domination over others, profit at any cost.

The unemployed poor are an example to the working poor, and to the working class what awaits them, what will happen to them if they stop working and if they stop fulfilling their obligations to their employer.

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Fear is the main motivation for everyone to look for a job, even one that does not meet their qualifications, expertise, experience, without setting conditions for what job they will get.

Fear spreads from the working poor to the poor, the middle class. Each lower class is an example of each upper class and stratum.

In reality, no one cares about the interest of humanity.

There is no welfare of people working in this way.

Each lower class serves as a fear example for each upper class.

This distorts human nature and the value system, and builds a distorted view of the value system of humanity.

A person who is at a higher level is more important than a person who is below that level.

Global neoliberal capitalism evaluates man according to his level, without being interested in his spiritual development and the meaning of his life and his existence.

Six categories of value systems must be distinguished:

- Personal value system / spiritual inclusive
- Spiritual value system public values
- A career value system that is not based on anything human
- Family value system
- Cultural value system
- Social value system

The creation of a level of poor, unemployed poor, poor leads to and is the basis for the commission of crimes by representatives at these levels. They not only can and do commit crimes, but also various violations.

They are susceptible to influence, to manipulation, to control, to influence, to management.

In addition, these strata are the needs of social services.

Social services, the judiciary, health care, education work in this direction are designed to create fear.

Most people succumb to lower and unethical moral attitudes.

The individual is concentrated on not falling from class to lower class. As well as move to the upper class. He is interested neither in the environment nor in what is happening.

Maslow groups human basic needs into five levels:

1. Physiological needs - necessary for life, such as food, water, shelter, clothing, sex, recreation.
2. Need for security - they provide physical and mental protection to the person and give him confidence, reliable work, pension system, working conditions and others.
3. Needs of commitment - those that involve someone or something - friendship, family, love, group participation, grind in an organization and others.
4. Needs of respect - and self-esteem - through which a person feels a person who is useful and important to himself and others. Confidence, status and aspirations.
5. Need for self-realization - a need that allows a person to express and develop their full potential.

This determines the respective strata of human society.

This pyramid of needs and opportunities is really responsible for c

This determines the respective strata of human society.

This pyramid of needs and opportunities is really responsible for the ability of man to participate in society.

Provided that a person strives to satisfy his physical needs because he receives a salary with which he can only pay his expenses and there is little money left to live on, then he is not interested in satisfying the above needs.

PYRAMID OF SURVIVAL AND LIFE

- 1 /. Satisfying the needs for life, food, survival
- 2 /. Satisfying the family, creating one
- 3 /. Satisfying the need for security, personal, family
- 4 /. Satisfaction of the status of respect depending on the achieved position and realization in the capitalist society.
- 5 /. Satisfying creative and other abilities.

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Depending on the satisfaction of these needs, the person is in the respective stratum.

Satisfying one need leads to a desire to satisfy the other, which is at a higher level. But this relocation is associated with the availability of adequate monetary resources per month, outside the cost of meeting basic needs.

If the corresponding resource is minimal, then the corresponding need is not satisfied.

If a need is not satisfied, then the person remains at this level a layer of interests, desires, opportunities. If there is not enough money for the entry of the next need, then it remains in the lower level.

A person who strives and struggles to satisfy his physical needs really cannot and does not have the time, the opportunity, the interest and the desire to be interested in politics, real politics, policy implementation, the political system, whether a party performs its.

le this is the restrictive line that limits a person's ability to be interested in power, politics, activities related to the distribution of public goods, theft, scams, crimes by people in power.

The need for self-transcendence is the desire to indulge in a higher goal related to spirituality and altruism, it is related to the corresponding monetary available excess threshold.

These are the real levels of opportunities and desires of the respective people, representatives of these levels, to be interested in politics, in a political system.

Everyone is at one of these levels and depending on these levels is the opportunity to participate in the management of society or not to participate in the system, government and others, or even be interested in it.

Global neoliberal capitalism does not stimulate the individual to be interested in what is applied by what he has created and how it is useful for the whole society.

This capitalism is not interested in satisfying the needs of the individual, it must satisfy its needs through its income and money. However, the needs may ultimately be different depending on its value system.

People in capitalism are kept under control, under management, under manipulation, man must produce, he is a necessary resource for production.

The goal of man is to satisfy his needs for himself and his family without complying with his value system, morals, honor, dignity, conscience.

The purpose of this capitalism is not to expand the consciousness of man to ever-comprehensive forms of community and society. The goal is to satisfy only the ego.

Global neoliberal capitalism undermines and destroys human human ideals.

This capitalism does not aim for abundance for all.

Capitalism does not create lasting harmonious ties for cooperation, the system and a single organism in society.

Capitalism creates only competition and opposition between people of any value system.

CAPITALISM governs man with the system of fear, repression, extortion, manipulation.

THE FEAR OF SURVIVAL is a key feature of capitalism.

It is difficult to survive.

Capitalism has developed only those high technologies and scientific discoveries that allow management, manipulation, control of people.

Global neoliberal capitalism and its ruling global Masonic mafia elite with its deep rule and state hide scientific discoveries that will provide free energy, new medicine, new medical care and tackling the most terrible diseases of mankind.

This capitalism hides scientific discoveries that are good for human existence.

This capitalism maintains excessively high prices - electricity, water, electricity.

Capitalism rules for the sole purpose of making huge profits.

There is a constant race for profits, control, people management.

There is a constant enrichment of a minority of the oligarchy, of Freemasons from the deep state and deep government.

The lives of billions of people are being devalued, human rights are being violated.

There is no predictability, no security, no satisfaction in life, both spiritually and in two ways.

There is no security in society, no justice.

There is a violation of the rights and freedoms of citizens.

Nobody cares about the value of human life. le human life has no value.

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Healthcare, education, medicine are aimed at the oligarchs,

The economy is aimed at increasing the welfare of a unit of people, the oligarchs.

Satisfaction of goods for every citizen is not pursued.

No one aims to improve the lives of the population.

There is no quality medicine. There is no access to medicine, no security for a normal income and life. There is no access, no equal opportunities for education and qualification.

People aim to satisfy their minimum subsistence, satisfy only their primary needs for securing their lives, but not other goals and motives.

One has no security, no protection in society, from laws, from order.

People are not looking for anything unreal, impossible for their right.

People want what belongs to them and what is not given to me by society and government.

People want peace and peaceful coexistence.

People want to meet their basic needs.

The problems of the consumer society of this global neoliberal capitalism run by the global Masonic mafia elite are enormous.

This can no longer continue. Value orientation is focused only on making money and profits in any way.

Consumer society leads to regression, disintegration, of human values, values, moral and ethical values, There is no real guarantee of rights and freedoms

This leads to destruction and self-destruction.

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The consumer format leads to a dead end, to decline.

Civilization needs new horizons, new freedoms, equality, justice, without inequalities.

We must create a new era of the existence of humanity, which will fill with a new value content of our lives, of our existence.

Only by creating a new system - new principles will humanity survive and survive. Respect and appreciation of human life is the most important thing in this new era.

The person should be given opportunities for happy existence and understanding of the purpose, mission, meaning of his life.

Building a society of MAN and HIS HUMANITY in the center of the ecological system - man nature, planet.

The new society must be a society of creation, of creativity, of development. Progress is possible only with the participation of all people in the creation of a society of creators, personalities - creators with honor, dignity, conscience, justice.

The goal is to improve the whole world, the whole environment, all societies,

The goal is human evolution, which requires an appropriate structure, rules, laws.

At the moment, no one believes in the prosperity of society, in the justice of society, in the equality of people, in their independence and equality.

Only lies, fraud, manipulation by politicians. No one believes in progress, development, evolution, development. Improvement.

No one believes in economic, technical, spiritual, progress,

Rich and poor, division of people, inequality of people.

They do not believe that prosperity encompasses all people and individuals.

That is why the poor and poverty are increasing.

Mankind is constantly dreaming of change and improvement.

The consumer society is at a dead end.

The consumer society develops hidden forms of slavery, indebtedness, inequalities.

This is a real disguised slave system.

The goal is spiritually free people and a corresponding society.

This society guarantees a dignified life, public goods and spiritual and moral development.

There is talk pro forma about ideals, about sublimity, but in reality it is a jungle.

The mafia and the global Masonic mafia-dominated elite ruled by capitalist society are fighting for territories, resources, assets, the conquest of a consumer society from which to make huge profits.

Everything that exists in modern society is real against man and his real spiritual essence.

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After all, here we are talking about and only about interests that are based on money, on power, on making profits.

In reality, this is not about protecting the interests of the whole society, but only of a group of people who control money, finances, government - the DEEP STATE AND THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE €

In reality, people have handed over their rights and freedoms to people with capital and finances, but in reality, with this transfer of freedoms and rights, people have also handed over public goods, which accumulate in a group of people.

What is needed is a process of returning these goods - which are ultimately societies - to society as a whole. In reality, man has lost his status as a man with his soul.

In the current society of global neoliberal capitalism, lies, slander, untruth, meanness, betrayal, selfishness rule.

Relationships between people relate only to benefits, gains, interests.

The real human nature of human relationships is lost.

4. WHAT A DEMOCRACY DEPENDS ON - REALITIES, IMPORTANT FACTORS FOR THE GOVERNANCE OF DEMOCRACY, PRINCIPLES OF DEMOCRACY

An essential feature of democracy is equality and freedoms.

Equality of all citizens before the law and equal access to power

In a representative democracy, all votes have equal weight, the possibility of citizens to become representatives is not limited, the freedom of citizens is ensured through legally established rights and freedoms.

Democratic systems contain internal mechanisms for separation of powers, unequal distribution of power, and potential violations of democratic principles by individual institutions.

This opposes democracy "government of the rulers", with an alternative system - monarchy, oligarchy - and timocracy. Right to participate in political life. Agreement between the rulers and the ruled - the voters. Direct democracy - selectivity of certain government positions.

Democracy is a way of life - with established social, economic and political equality

The word democracy comes from the ancient Greek language meaning "democracy."

The leading role is played by the people.

Lincoln's phrase addresses two aspects of democracy:

First, it answers the question "who rules" - the people, directly or through persons elected by them

The second answers the question "how is it governed" - a way in which governing activities are carried out by the people for the people.

In connection with the question of who governs the problems of democracy, they are in connection with the subjects - people, class, stratum, state.

The rules and principles of people's participation in politics and governance.

An essential concept for management is:

- Procedures - the rules for the governing political process
- Substantive - effective. The result of democratic governance -
- both rights and obligations

DEMOCRACY depends on the following factors and the degree of their development in society:

Important factors for governance in a country:

Justice in society - state, court, prosecutor's office

- Population structure, and its role
- The official doctrines
- The structure of society
- The characteristics of the elite
- The institutions of power
- The type of economy
- Theories of ownership
- The attitude to the law and
- The judicial system

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- The attitude to knowledge
- Information and dissemination of information,
- The attitude to politics
- Population inequality
- The structure of the population of cultural, social, political, ideological, ethnic significance

Fundamental rights

Inequality in society

The middle class

Values, morals, identities, cultural models

LAWS

BASIC LAW - constitution or others

FUNDAMENTAL HUMAN RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS

OBLIGATIONS under the laws

DEMOCRACY AND THE DEGREE OF DEMOCRACY DEPEND ON THE FOLLOWING FACTORS AND THEIR DEGREES AS FOLLOWS / short description /:

MANAGEMENT

Degree of transparent governance in the country

Degree of government in the country in favor of third parties

Degree of government in the state in favor of the oligarchy

Degree of taxation in favor of the oligarchy

Degree of utilization of public resource for the benefit of third parties

Degree of utilization of public resources in public procurement in favor of a specific third party

Degree of uncontrolled spending of public resources

Degree of lack of control over corrupt decisions

PARLIAMENT

Degree of dependence on the oligarchy

Degree of dependence on the mafia

Degree of disregard / non-application / non-compliance with the laws

Degree of adoption of laws in violation of the public interest

Degree of adoption of laws in violation of the Constitution

Degree of passing laws in favor of the oligarchy

Degree of adoption of laws violating human rights

Degree of dependence on different interests / lobbying

WHAT DEPENDS ON INJUSTICE / JUSTICE in a country with democratic governance in modern times:

DEGREE OF LEGALITY - LAWS ADOPTED

LEVEL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS

DEGREE OF DUALITY OF LAW ENFORCEMENT

DEGREE OF DUALITY OF LAWS ADOPTED

DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AND CONTRADICTION OF THE LAWS ADOPTED WITH THE BASIC LAW OF

DEGREE OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS

DEGREE OF EQUALITY

DEGREE OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF THE LAW BY JUDGES

DEGREE OF CONTROL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE LAW BY PROSECUTORS

LEVEL OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS BY GOVERNMENT, MINISTERS,

LEVEL OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS BY MUNICIPAL / LOCAL AUTHORITIES

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DEGREE OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS BY MINISTERS AND PRIME MINISTERS BY THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE ON THE EXECUTIVE POWER
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE FROM THE MAFIA IN ITS BENEFIT
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF MAFIA JUDGES
DEGREE OF BREACH OF LAWS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF IMPUNITY OF JUDGES
DEGREE OF IMPUNITY OF PROSECUTORS
LEVEL OF IMPUNITY OF CITIZENS
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS FROM THE EVIDENCE
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS - IMPACTED PRACTICE
DEGREE OF NON-ENFORCEMENT OF JUDGMENTS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF NON-COMPLIANCE OF DIRECTIVE ORDINANTS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF NON-ENFORCEMENT OF JUDGMENTS
LEVEL OF NON-APPLICATION OF JUDGMENTS
DEGREE OF VIOLATION OF JUDGMENTS
DEGREE OF NON - COMPLIANCE WITH LAWS
LEVEL OF NON - APPLICATION OF LAWS
DEGREE OF BREACH OF LAWS
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE COURT
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE STATE APPARATUS
DEGREE OF MAFIONIZATION IN THE LOCAL MUNICIPAL APPARATUS
DEGREE OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CONSTITUTION

HUMAN RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS

LEVEL OF EXERCISE OF BASIC CIVIL RIGHTS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION BETWEEN DIFFERENT GROUPS OF PEOPLE
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION ON RELIGIOUS BASIS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION ON A CULTURAL BASIS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AT EDUCATIONAL LEVEL - CENSUS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AT THE PUBLIC LEVEL
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AT SOCIAL LEVEL
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AT BUSINESS LEVEL - MONOPOLY, OLIGOPOL AND OTHERS

CORRUPTION

DEGREE OF CORRUPTION WITH JUDGES
DEGREE OF CORRUPTION WITH PROSECUTORS
DEGREE OF CORRUPTION WITH STATES / MUNICIPAL / MINISTERS / PRIME MINISTERS
DEGREE OF MAFIA AND MAFIOTISM IN A COUNTRY

HUMAN RIGHTS

DEGREE OF RESPECT FOR HUMAN RIGHTS
LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS LAWS

ELECTIONS

DEGREE OF EDUCATION OF VOTERS
LEVEL OF EDUCATION - SECONDARY EDUCATION
LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION OF MINORITIES WITH LOW EDUCATION
LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION OF LOW-INCOME MINORITIES

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LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION OF MIDDLE INCOME PEOPLE
LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION OF LOW INCOME PEOPLE
DEGREE OF ELECTION COUNTERFEITING
METHODS USED TO FALSE THE ELECTIONS

INEQUALITIES and ELECTIONS

LEVEL OF PROFIT OF THE POPULATION
LEVEL OF CITIZEN PARTICIPATION IN ELECTIONS / BY AGE /
LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION OF CITIZENS IN ELECTIONS / BY INCOME /
DEGREE OF PARTICIPATION OF CITIZENS IN ELECTIONS / BY EDUCATION /

IMPLEMENTATION OF LAWS BY GOVERNMENT

DEGREE OF IMPLEMENTATION OF LAWS BY MINISTERS
DEGREE OF IMPLEMENTATION OF LAWS BY THE PRIME MINISTER
DEGREE OF VIOLATION OF THE LAWS BY MINISTERS
DEGREE OF VIOLATION OF LAWS BY THE PRIME MINISTER

DEGREE OF VALUE SYSTEMS / MORALS

- Personal value system and spiritual value system
- Spiritual value system public values
- Career value system
- Family value system
- Cultural value system
- Social value system

INEQUALITY IN SOCIETY

LEVEL OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on education /
DEGREE OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on secondary education
DEGREE OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on higher education /
DEGREE OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on age /
DEGREE OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on income /
DEGREE OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on religion
DEGREE OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on the culture
DEGREE OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on the minority /
DEGREE OF SOCIAL INEQUALITY / depending on the assets

MORALITY AND DEGREE OF MORALITY

Morality is the distinction between intentions, decisions, and actions against those that are good and right and those that are wrong and bad. Morality is an essential part of the standards and principles that are derived from the code of ethics of the respective guild and in a democratic society.

Degree of Morality - "honesty", "integrity", "justice", "kindness", "right", "conscience".

However, moral norms and principles in a democracy are uniform, although there are different moral systems. After the law, morality is the second source of law in countries that have adopted the continental legal system. If such a morality with the respective qualities is missing, then there is no right and the law is not realized, is not realized, is not fulfilled.

Ethics, on the other hand, is a branch of philosophy that deals with moral issues. Ethics includes and encompasses the moral principles of a society, culture, person, group.

Morality is limited as a system of duty, obligation, principles of conduct, justice.

On the other hand, morality contains a value system. This value system is a set of ethical values of a person, organization, society, group, which represent a standard for human behavior in all situations - group, family, society.

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DEGREE OF INJUSTICE in a society - depends on the degree of MAFIOTISM in a society, the degree of corruption among law enforcement agencies and those involved in passing laws, the degree of trust of civil society in all participants in government - court, prosecutor's office, how and whether judges and prosecutors comply with the law, enforce the law, apply the law, do not enforce, violate the law
prosecutor's office, state, municipalities.

The DEGREE OF DEMOCRATIZATION OF A SOCIETY depends on the respective DEGREE OF UNJUSTICE / JUSTICE.

FAIR FORMULA / INJUSTICE:

JUSTICE / INJUSTICE = POWER + Influence + Relationships + Interests + MONEY / AND + Mafia structure / internal or external / + Monopoly rights / rights + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility to make an alternative decision - Obligation - Responsibility - morality ethics - observance / application / implementation of the law by judges / prosecutors / statesmen - Control / Sanctions - Corruption - Mafiaization - TRUST / DEGREE OF TRUST.

WHAT DEPENDS ON INJUSTICE / JUSTICE IN A SOCIETY:

DEGREE OF LEGALITY - LAWS ADOPTED
LEVEL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS
DEGREE OF DUALITY OF LAW ENFORCEMENT
DEGREE OF DUALITY OF LAWS ADOPTED
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AND CONTRADICTION OF THE LAWS ADOPTED WITH THE BASIC LAW OF
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS
DEGREE OF EQUALITY
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF THE LAW BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE LAW BY PROSECUTORS
LEVEL OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS BY GOVERNMENT, MINISTERS,
LEVEL OF CONTROL OF ENFORCEMENT OF LAWS BY MUNICIPAL / LOCAL AUTHORITIES
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF LAWS BY MINISTERS AND PRIME MINISTERS BY THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE ON THE EXECUTIVE POWER
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE FROM THE MAFIA IN ITS BENEFIT
DEGREE OF DEPENDENCE OF MAFIA JUDGES
DEGREE OF BREACH OF LAWS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF IMPUNITY OF JUDGES
DEGREE OF IMPUNITY OF PROSECUTORS
LEVEL OF IMPUNITY OF CITIZENS
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS FROM THE EVIDENCE
DEGREE OF CONTROL OF JUDGMENTS - IMPACTED PRACTICE
DEGREE OF NON-ENFORCEMENT OF JUDGMENTS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF NON-COMPLIANCE OF DIRECTIVE ORDINANTS BY JUDGES
DEGREE OF NON-ENFORCEMENT OF JUDGMENTS
LEVEL OF NON-APPLICATION OF JUDGMENTS
DEGREE OF VIOLATION OF JUDGMENTS
DEGREE OF NON - COMPLIANCE WITH LAWS
LEVEL OF NON - APPLICATION OF LAWS
DEGREE OF BREACH OF LAWS
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE COURT
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE
DEGREE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE STATE APPARATUS
DEGREE OF MAFIONIZATION IN THE LOCAL MUNICIPAL APPARATUS
DEGREE OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CONSTITUTION

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LEVEL OF EXERCISE OF BASIC CIVIL RIGHTS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION BETWEEN DIFFERENT GROUPS OF PEOPLE
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION ON RELIGIOUS BASIS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION ON A CULTURAL BASIS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AT EDUCATIONAL LEVEL - CENSUS
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION OF COMMUNITY NJVZH
DEGREE OF CONFRONTATION AT BUSINESS LEVEL - MONOPOLY, OLIGOPOL AND OTHERS
DEGREE OF CORRUPTION WITH JUDGES
DEGREE OF CORRUPTION WITH PROSECUTORS
LEVEL OF CORRUPTION WITH STATES / MUNICIPAL
DEGREE OF THE MAFIA

AREAS OF DISTRIBUTION OF INJUSTICE

Injustice can be found in court, prosecutor's office, state, ministers, executive institutions, regulatory bodies, controlling bodies, bodies protecting and controlling the rights and freedoms of citizens, personal data, discrimination, executive services. They depend on the mafiaization of a society, on practices, traditions, political and economic development, the specifics of a society, the socio-cultural environment, laws, morals, rules, norms, morals and ethics of behavior of citizens, judges, prosecutors, statesmen, employees and others.

Areas of manifestation of corruption are:

- 1 /. The sphere of state administration. This includes government, government departments, and institutions, local governments, and others.
- 2 /. The sphere of politics-. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non-profit associations. Adoption of laws that are unconstitutional and the basic law protecting rights.
- 3 /. The sphere of the judiciary / judges / prosecutors / investigators
- 4 /. The sphere of law enforcement institutions / prosecutor's office, investigation services, police /
- 5 /. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance and others.
- 6 /. The sphere of the private sector - business organizations, companies both local and international, global and transnational.
- 7 /. The field of media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /
- 8 / The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

Justice / injustice is mostly characteristic of the public sector, but it is also found in the private sector.

Justice / injustice depends on the mafiaization of a society, on corruption and the degree of corruption in a society.

FORMS OF INJUSTICE / JUSTICE IN THE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

The forms of injustice / fairness in public administration are the following:

1. Failure to comply with a lawful request by a person entitled to do so by an employee of the relevant administration. Manifesting in open refusal, tacit refusal and others.
2. When the government or the respective administration, body, institution is a seller and does not fulfill the law, it violates the law, not applied by the law.
3. When the government or the respective administration, body, institution is a buyer or consumer of certain services and does not fulfill the law, it violates the law, does not apply the law.
4. When state and other institutions - municipal carry out right-wing transactions, and do not comply with the law, violate the law, do not apply the law.
5. When the executive power controls financial and credit institutions, companies with licenses, companies with concessions, permits and others, and does not comply with the law, violates the law, does not apply the law.
6. When the executive power distributes limited funds, subsidies, grants, investments, social payments and others and does not comply with the law, it violates the law, does not apply the law.

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7. When there is a service for granting and permitting specific activities, permits, licenses and other regimes for performing a specific activity and does not comply with the law, violates the law, does not apply the law

8. When collecting taxes, fees, customs duties - does not comply with the law, violates the law, violates the law, does not apply the law

9. When collecting fines, sanctions - does not comply with the law, violates the law, violates the law, does not apply the law

10. When state and other types of employees are authorized and authorized to perform control functions and to sanction third parties or companies in case of non-compliance and do not comply with the law, do not apply the law, violate the law, violate the law in favor of private interests.

11. When government or other types of employees have important inside information and do not comply with the law, do not apply the law, violate the law in someone's private interests

12. When there is non-transparency in decision-making and implementation of a decision or choice of decision.

JUSTICE / JUSTICE IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

The monopoly on the judiciary and the maintenance of public order is the most important prerequisite for the generation of corrupt practices in the judiciary and the police.

An important factor is the inaccuracy, incompleteness, the presence of gaps in the relevant laws, regulations, procedures, deadlines, inconsistency of laws, inaccuracy of procedures, violation of procedures and deadlines in the judiciary, the feeling of impunity by magistrates, police, prosecutors, investigators.

Corruption in the judiciary and the police is the most important factor in the spread, imposition, growth of corruption in the entire public sector.

It generates a sense of impunity for corrupt officials, a sense of injustice among the oppressed, a sense of a double standard of law for different strata and groups of people.

THE SPECIFICITY OF JUSTICE / CORRUPTION IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

1. The monopoly of knowledge and skills.

2. Presence of omissions, inconsistencies between different laws.

3. Failure to comply with deadlines and procedures in court proceedings.

4. Personnel crisis in the judiciary. The promotion of junior judges, relatives of senior judges, prosecutors known to senior judges and prosecutors, etc.

5. Crisis in the objective appointment and promotion of judges, prosecutors, investigators. There is political influence here, as well as influence from the executive branch.

6. Simultaneous action of legal norms contradictory to incompatibility

7. Existence of practical lack of responsibility and responsibility for poorly done work, for illegal decision.

8. Lack of clear rules for assessing the professional qualities of employees.

9. Lack of professional traditions.

10. Lack of limitation of competencies.

Other areas of corruption - politics, economics and the public sector - will not be addressed in this report.

5. GLOBAL NEOLIBERAL CAPITALISM and Principles of the Global Masonic Mafia Elite and its Deep Governance and Deep State and Its Consumer Society

The global Masonic mafia elite and the deep and deep state governed by it is a corporate, militarized, functionally defined, mafia group of people who run and own financial, banking, corporate, IT companies, not elected by the citizens of the countries that actually run not only a specific country, but also a group of countries, on the principles of Mafia and financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism.

The global Masonic mafia elite and its deep government and deep state have corrupted and mafiotized all spheres of society on which the government of a country, of a union depends - in the case of the European Commission and the European Union, the United States and other countries where they rule. people of the deep state.

All members of the global Masonic mafia elite and deep government and deep state are Freemasons and belong to different secret societies, no matter which. For years, all secret societies have been occupied from within by the representatives and bearers

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of the goals and aspirations of the Illuminati for a new world genocide and dictatorship over humanity. For these Masons the oath is to obey the law of the lodge and not to comply with any other laws - those of states, international law, unions and others and to do everything in the name and for the benefit of the lodge, observing only the laws of the lodge, but not to the state concerned, to international law, even to commit crimes, to help members of the lodge when they are in trouble, and to carry out the plan of the lodge. All laws and rules are subject to a vow of ideology and faith in Lucifer and the church of Lucifer / Satan.

And the plan is one - to conquer the world, to rule the world by one world government, only by them - the global Masonic mafia elite.

Concept - Prof. Momchil Dobrev

The global Masonic mafia elite and ruled by it DEEP GOVERNANCE AND DEEP GOVERNMENT is an organization, structure, government, kleptocracy, and cryptocracy of a group of people from the financial banking, resource, technology, corporate elite that GLOBALANALISM IN THE GLOBALISM countries of the principles of Mafioticism and of the financial bank resource technological mafiotized Materialism.

AREAS OF GOVERNANCE, CONTROL, THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE MANAGED BY IT, THE MAFIA AND MAFIOTISM IN THE ERA OF GLOBAL NEOLIBERAL CAPITALISM

The global Masonic mafia elite and deep governance and the deep state can be found in all spheres of public life, in all states, governments.

The spheres of action, goals, tasks, management, control, manifestation of global Yamason mafia elite and the deep state ruled by it and the global Masonic mafia elite through mafia and on the basis of financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism through the mafia are as follows:

-1 /. The sphere of state administration. This includes governments, prime ministers, ministers, government departments and institutions, local authorities and others, their control through compromising and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

-2 /. The sphere of politics. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non-profit associations, the degradation of the political elite, their control through compromising, and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

-3 /. Control and management of national security systems, secret services, intelligence services. Control and management of the management and administration of intelligence services, intelligence agencies, internal security departments, space intelligence services, central security services, national security services, intelligence and counterintelligence departments, intelligence departments of the Ministry of Defense, naval intelligence, air services, secret services, secret services

4 /. Control and management of the sphere of military structures, defense structures, defense structures, military-industrial complex

5 /. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance, etc.,

- 6 /. The sphere of the private sector, companies, corporations,

- 7 /. The sphere of the media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /, their control and management through racketeering, coercion, pressure, sanctions and others.

- 8 / The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

9 /. Banking and financial sector

10 /. Social networks and information technologies

11 /. The sphere of the judicial system / judges, prosecutors, investigators /, their control through addictions - bribes, gifts, excursions, knotrol through compromising, and other addictions - sexual, gambling and others.

12 /. The sphere of law enforcement institutions / prosecutor's office, investigation services, police /, their control through addictions, bribes, and others.

13 /. Control and management and conquest is the indebtedness of a country through the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, the European Central Bank, the International Bank for Settlements and other world banks.

14 /. Control and management of monopoly companies, controlling and having monopoly influence all over the world through investment companies, owned by the global Masonic mafia elite - BlackRock and other companies.

15 /. Leadership and intelligence management of the state treasury,

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16. The overthrow of regimes through "yellow", "orange" revolutions and the appointment of governments, presidents to serve the interests of the deep state

17 /. Provoking occasions for starting and starting wars against countries whose territories with the respective natural resources are of interest to the representatives of the deep state.

18 /. Imposition of policy in relevant countries that are in the economic interests of the deep state and their profits from it.

19 /. Imposition of a policy in the case of NATO for the purpose of threats, wars against third countries from the territories of foreign countries.

20 /. Imposing a world government A new world order that will allow them to more easily govern countries, nations, peoples, economies, industries, finance, capital.

21 /. Creating conditions, causing chaos through various schemes and occasions - wars, refugee waves, crises - social, social, political, economic, state schemes with the ultimate goal of profits - economic, financial - profit and personal gain.

22 /. Management, control, manipulation, zombies of the civil society, through non-governmental organizations, their financing / example SOROS /,

23 /. Imposing their requirements for military budgets of all countries in order to sell weapons from their companies in the military-industrial complex to countries, countries. 21 /. Control of criminal groups and groups

24 /. Control of trade, military, criminal groups, the defense industry, the financial sector, corporate media and counterterrorism.

25 /. Managing the military budgets of states, at least more than half goes to military spending and the purchase of equipment and weapons.

26 /. Control and management of the military-industrial complex

27 / Control and management of the state money, budgets, of the respective state

28 /. Management of many non-governmental national and international structures - the Council on Foreign Relations, the Royal Institute of International Affairs, the Trust Commission, the Bilderberg Group, the Club of Rome, the Committee 300,

29 /. Supranational governance of the countries of the planet.

30 /. Management of International Institutions - UN, UNICEF, World Health Organization,

31 /. Committing crimes against people, individuals, services

32 /. Imposing globalization as an ideology

33 /. Imposing the ideology and society of lesbianism, gay, bisexual and transgender people - LGBT people as a leader at the state level.

34 /. Use of compromising control of individuals - politicians and any others on whom depends the state and other decisions responsible for society as a whole.

35 /. Create a program, plan, and accomplish the task of destroying Christianity.

36 / annihilation of the family as the basic building block of the society.

37 /. Targeted organization of migration through refugee waves, crises

38 /. Control and management of the electoral process in each country, imposing organization, management of the electoral process through various schemes of falsification and fraud.

39 /. Social terrorism of society from a moral, spiritual, economic point of view.

40 /. Total control of the population, by monitoring and controlling the permanent address, social activity on Facebook, Twitter, etc., driving licenses, watched or recorded movies, activity on various blogs, viewing or sending photos, detention by the police, subway trips, credit and debit cards, financial information, viewed photos, sent photos, face recognition by surveillance cameras, sent e-mails, received emails, searching for information on the network, health card, education, train tickets, bus, plane, recorded mobile applications, used applications, traffic, online transactions, text messages sent, and messages

41 /. Terrorist actions through the US and NATO and other military organizations

42 /. Terrorist actions through private formations

43 /. Destruction and collapse of the education system

44 /. killing the national achievements of democracy and erasing history

45 /. destruction of the social system

46 /. polarization of society

47 /. destruction of national values

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- 48 /. destruction of the national culture
- 49 /. destruction of rights and freedoms
- 50 /. destruction of the middle class
- 51 /. increasing poverty and inequality
- 52 /. increase begging
- 53 /. Indebtedness of countries, governments through the IMF, WB, ECB
- 54 /. Dependence of the media - television, radio, newspapers, magazines,
- 55 /. Control, management of the drug business since the 18th century by the black aristocracy
- 56 /. Creating inequalities in society, managing these inequalities, destroying the middle class, with the ultimate goal of enslaving society.
- 57 /. Creating conditions for control and management of the economies of entire countries with the sole purpose of personal gain.
- 58 /. Creation of an elite of universities - of a Masonic mafia-dominated global elite to rule states and other institutions for the benefit of the Global Masonic elite.
- 59 /. Control and management of education in a country in order to blunt, greater control and management of the masses and the younger generation in order to zombie and manage and control at any level - emotional, educational, social and others.
- 60 /. Creating a system for SOCIAL GENOCYD
- 61 /. Control is the management of health care with the ultimate goal of reducing the world's population,
- 62 /. Control and management of the system of drug development and dependence of the population on drugs.
- 63 /. Control and management of patents and developments and elimination of scientists who created discoveries that can improve people's lives.
- 64 /. Control and liquidate scientists, creators of drugs, but new methods of treatment that are cheap and hinder the wealth of the elite.
- 65 /. Control and liquidation of scientists creating systems for zero-point generators and free energy generators.
- 66 /. Control, management, drug production and addiction among the population with the ultimate goal of profit.
- 67. Control, creation of GMO products, food, for the purpose of profit and reduction of the population.
- 68 /. Control and management of the population through food, lethal medicine, lethal vaccines, psychiatric medicines, deadly food, deadly grain, deadly sweeteners, GMOs, deadly water, air,
- 69 /. Control and management of the media, conquest of the media, and propaganda only of their goals, ideas, aspirations, plans, disguised under the slogan that care for humanity and the people in it.
- 70 /. Creating institutions that will govern countries, policies, such as the UN, UNICEF and others
- 71 /. Control of the special and secret services through their Freemasons to serve their lodges and personal interests, but not the laws of the respective state.
- 72 /. Creating their own structures to include their people who would later govern and lead states - Council on Foreign Relations, 1921 and branches - Institute for Pacific Relations - New York, Center for Foreign Policy Studies - Paris, Institute for Foreign Policy - Hamburg, Royal Institute of International Affairs -1920, Bilberberg Group - 1954, Club of Rome - 1968, Trilateral Commission 1973, to determine the international policies of states, to govern states.
- 73 /. Creation of an elite by the University of Global Masonic Mafia Elite - Yale University, Harvard, Columbia, Cornell University, New York University, Sarah Lawrence's University, Stanford University, University of Chicago, John Copkins, Brown University,
- 74 /. Control and management of all Masonic lodges - Knights Templar, Freemasonry, Rosicrucians, lodge of Gnosticism, Kabbalism, the Illuminati Freemasons through the principles of the Church of Lucifer.
- 75 /. Control and management of the elite and societies and states through Foundations - Rockefeller Foundation, Ford Foundation, Carnegie Endowment, Clinton Foundation,
- 76 /. Management and control of media, owned by television - BBC, CBC, CNN, CBS, ABC, CNN and others, telegraph agencies - Associated Press, Reuters and others, newspapers - New York Times, Washington Post, Wall Street Journal, Boston Globe, Baltimore Sun, Chicago Sun Times, Los Angeles Times, Houston Post, Minneapolis Star / Tribune and others, magazines -. Fortune, Time, Life, Money, People, Newsweek, Business Week, Readers Digest, US News and World Report, and others, dozens of publishers,
- 77 /. Propaganda and manipulation to reduce critical thinking

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- increasing the closedness, depression, dependence, feelings of slavery and dependence on the decisions and actions of the government
- turning one's back on the real facts and evidence
- dependence on propaganda
- dependence on the promoted fear and stress
- increase in mental illness
- increase in drug abuse
- increase in the number of homeless people
- increase in the unemployed
- increase in malnourished people
- increase in malignant incurable diseases
- increase in theft
- increase in crime
- increase in homicides
- increasing the bankruptcies of companies
- reducing the duration of

78 /. Control by the global Yamason mafia elite of each state and its management through the control and management of the special services and secret services of the respective state.

79 /. Control by the global Masonic mafia elite of all Masonic and other and all kinds of Masonic lodges around the world.

80 /. Control and management of the election, election and appointment of presidents, prime ministers, chancellors in the respective countries from the structures of the deep state.

81 /. Election fraud in order to win the election of this party, which is ruled by the global Masonic and mafia elite and the deep government and the deep state. Managing the process of election fraud in countries ruled by the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state.

82 /. The global Masonic mafia elite rules, controls the deep state in every country on the planet.

Deep governance and the deep state and its representatives act as a shadow government. Deep governance and the deep state do not respect the rights, freedoms, constitutions of the respective state, the treaties for the formation of alliances, such as the European Union.

In reality, Deep Governance and Deep State use the following undemocratic models of governance as follows:

- Autocracy
- Oligarchy
- Plutocracy
- Kleptocracy
- Corporatocracy
- Cryptocracy

All these systems of government are managed on the basis of the principles of MAFIOTISM and the Financial Bank Resource Technological Mafia Materialism.

6. BASIC PRINCIPLES OF HUMAN SOCIETY ESTABLISHED ON THE BASIS OF THE THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM by Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobрева

Direct democracy IN ALL AREAS AND AT ALL LEVELS

1 /. At the center of this society, created on the basis of THEORY YANA SOCIO-HUMANISM of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobрева, is man and the environment in which he lives, which is part of him and inextricably linked to him.

Human life and its value and its guarantee.

Guarantee of life - every person is guaranteed security of basic necessities of life, including, wound, housing, health care, medical care, education, social security.

The scientific, production and technological activity of the society must be directed mostly and only to the improvement of the quality of human life in the respective ecological environment.

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Politics and economics must ensure economic stability, no inflation, any crises, stable, equal, comparable prices around the world, a fixed minimum taxation, a stable currency that is independent of inflation, crises, etc., and the corresponding rate of return for the respective goods, which is the basis of governance in a society.

This is the highest value, the goal of a society is to preserve and guarantee and ensure the value life of every person. There is nothing more precious than human life,

2 /. Human rights and freedoms

All human beings are born free and with the same rights as human beings. Everyone has the right to choose, everyone has rights and freedoms, and society must protect these rights and freedoms of all citizens. These rights and freedoms are for everyone and not for certain classes, groups of people. No one has the right to take away people's rights and freedoms. No one has the right to threaten these rights and freedoms with his decision - be it government, community and others. This includes the fundamental right to political equality, not only in other respects.

3 /. Human security and safety

No one has the right to threaten man and his security, no one has the right to threaten man and his rights and freedoms. The system and society must protect it.

4 /. UNIFORM WORLD SERVICE FOR GUARANTEE OF PEACE, fight against emergencies. Representatives of such countries as the United States, China, Russia, Germany, Great Britain, France will take part in this council, which will guarantee and ensure peace on the planet.

5 /. There is generally available information for everyone about everything that is available in society.

Everyone should have the opportunity and access to receive full information about everything - about society, about policies, about the budget, about the funds spent, about public projects, about investments in society, about movement, the distribution of public goods, the distribution of public goods. public money. Everyone should have access to all the information about how the decisions of the society, the tasks, the plans of the society are implemented.

Independence of the media - mandatory presence of public media to provide such access and to provide complete information to the public.

6 /. System of development of human creative abilities and their satisfaction

Society to man, for his development and existence in the spiritual and any other sphere in the respective ecological system, which is connected in the system man, nature, planet.

Society to man, his development and existence, in full, spiritual plan, material plan, social plan, ecological plan

The ideology - the system must be to create conditions for the care of man, for his development - both spiritual and material, spiritual, social, environmental sphere, to meet all his needs from the Maslow pyramid fully and comprehensively.

The main priority of the SOCIETY BASED ON THE THEORY OF SOCIO-HUMANISM is the development of man, his spirituality, respectively his development in the professional sphere, in the spiritual sphere, development of his abilities, discovery of his personal abilities, development of these abilities, their manifestation in society.

Raising a high pedestal of moral, ethical values of man, spiritual and moral aspirations and desires of man, humanity, mutual respect, self-esteem, development of human relationships.

Education of man in the moral and ethical values of society, stimulation of the moral and ethical values of every person

Creating conditions for the inclusion of the individual in and with society, and for the development of the individual

Everyone in this society has the right, opportunity, access and freedom to develop, to develop their abilities, has the right to development and self-realization, Creating conditions for the development of creative abilities and gifts of man at any age.

Raising a pedestal of human spiritual development.

Education should not only be accessible to all, possible for all, and free and equal, but such education should be for the person throughout his life.

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Education after secondary education, education among higher education, education after 25 years to his pigsty in which to allow a person to develop, develop and discover his new abilities creatively, and to support such development and realization by society.

Society guarantees and creates conditions for the realization of human creativity in every field.

7 /. Justice, Equality.,

All natural resources belong to society and man in particular. They are public goods. And they must be distributed equally among all members of a society.

Any monopolization of resources is excluded, and any kind of irrational anti-human anti-social use of these resources is excluded.

Resources are distributed fairly among all members of the community.

Everyone is guaranteed employment at his or her request. Wages are the same in every society for the same specialty, profession, position, qualification,

Everyone has the right to private property and income, as well as from an activity corresponding to his activity.

This society guarantees justice in society at all levels of the organization of society.

le this society guarantees full justice and solves the problems of justice / injustice described in the previous chapter.

8 /. Referendum democracy system

Citizenship . Everyone has the right to participate in the government of the respective state and society, to participate in the respective adoption of laws, for the improvement of people's lives, for the implementation of laws, for the adoption of the respective budgets for realization of goals, plans, for adoption of plans for development in all spheres of society.

The solution of all tasks concerning society, in the social sphere, in the ecological sphere, in the economic sphere, and in all other spheres will be considered by referendums, which may be attended by appropriately educated people who will have a minimum level of education.

9 /. Labor system. Everyone has the right to work and to work. He works depending on qualification, specialization, profession, experience. In the system of the society based on the Theory of Socio-Humanism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobрева, each person will have the right to work 3 days a week, and in the other two days of the week he must develop, participate in various courses for retraining, for development, for training in specialties and subjects that interest him and develop his creative abilities.

Every two days a week, each person must deal with their personal development in various specialties, professions, creative abilities.

If someone does not want to work, he will be provided, he will be guaranteed medicine, health care, education, social activities in the minimum amount, but there will be a requirement to train, develop and discover their other abilities, which may possibly be realized at a later stage.

10 /. The economic system in the Society based on the Theory of Socio-Humanism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobрева

Apart from the fact that in every country there must be a direct democracy and a system of drawing lots for professional positions, control at any level, control in every field and every ministry that is specialized. The control will be carried out by councils on a rotating basis by qualified specialists with the respective status - selected by lot from the citizens. The control will be performed regarding the activities performed under the respective plan - programs, and control of the respective budget of the respective activity.

In the Economy, all companies that provide basic resources - such as electricity, water, electricity, gas, oil, gasoline, other raw materials - must be state-run companies. Companies producing basic foodstuffs and foodstuffs must be state-run companies, which will be managed by the relevant ministry at the rate of profit.

THE PROFIT RATE INDICATOR will determine the limits of the prices of goods on the market, which will ensure fairness of the prices of goods necessary for human existence.

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It will be possible to form joint companies in public-private partnership, which will deal with innovations and whose products will benefit the people and the whole society, as the state will determine the rate of profit of the respective manufactured goods and services.

IMPLEMENTATION OF NEW FORMS OF HUMAN RELATIONSHIPS IS IMPORTANT.

EIGHT FUNDAMENTALS OF THE CREATIVE SOCIETY.

ERADICATION OF CRIME.

There is crime where there are conditions for such and its existence.

le these are opportunities that are available from the conditions that cause and generate crime.

Crime is present where there is a need for something, a shortcoming.

If a person has everything, no need, no social protection, then he would never commit a crime.

He really has everything he needs.

When the minimum need of the person is the one available to him, it arises naturally if there are conditions in the person himself for the need to commit a crime.

Therefore, when society satisfies and satisfies all human needs

This is also related to education, healthcare, social system.

THE SYSTEM OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY - THROUGH REFERENDUMS

The current system of government is not a democracy at all, as it is not a real democracy, but rather an aristocratic mafia oligarchy of the global Masonic mafia elite and its deep rule in the deep state.

The mechanism underlying this sham democracy is elections. Elections are elected on the basis of citizens' votes.

These representatives, in turn, elect their proxies and representatives in the executive branch.

History proves that these representatives represent an elite that is mafia-like, corrupt, that looks only at its own personal interests and, if it enters the relevant parliament, forgets about its promises, and aims and carries out activities that only bring it millions of profits.

le this elite becomes an aristocratic oligarchy, which really represents and ultimately protects the interests of themselves and the few who give money and bribes, lobby with money and funds, property and others.

In the current "democracies", a voting procedure has been adopted and chosen.

Really so far. In reality, companies and banks finance both countries in one election - for example, in the United States and the two candidates of the two major parties, and whoever wins after that will work for them again.

The current systems cannot be democracies because of the electoral systems and the established system of the global Masonic mafia elite to falsify elections.

With the establishment of this type of government in the late 18th century in Britain, then in the United States, and in France after 1789. its creators knew that this had nothing to do with democracy a.

They had no real intention of creating a demonstration.

All these systems were created by a Masonic mafia elite and the deep government and deep state ruled by it.

For this Masonic mafia elite, the creation of democracy was really the creation of anarchy, and the rule of the common people.

Thus, they create government through representation, which has nothing to do with democracy.

They really wanted to end the rule of the aristocracy and replace it with their mafia-style system of government in which they would rule, to draw on the goods.

In reality, democracy is translated as "democracy", and that state power comes from the people for the benefit of the people and is divided into:

- Consensus democracy
- Referendum direct democracy
- Representative democracy through elected representatives

By people is meant the citizens.

Essential characteristics of democracy are equality and freedom.

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Equality of all citizens in the law and equal access to power.

The freedom of citizens is ensured through established rights and freedoms in relevant laws.

In a representative democracy, all votes have equal weight, but in reality the ability of citizens to become representatives is limited, their ability to come to power is limited.

In reality, however, there is no real political equality in the current systems.

Equality in representative government is only fictitious, formal, imaginary.

It was clear to the founders of democracy that no one would be overthrown by voting, and that the poor would never take power by voting in elections.

Just because elections are a form of falsification of free choice.

That is why it is convenient for all this global Masonic mafia elite to call this "democracy", which, however, has nothing to do with democracy.

A caste of politicians is being created.

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF DEMOCRACY ARE:

The main element that shows the existence of a DEMOCRACY is the TRUE POLITICAL EQUALITY OF THE CITIZENS, which does not really exist at the moment.

Not socially, economically, physically, culturally, ethnically, etc. and POLITICAL EQUALITY - EQUALITY IN POLITICAL DECISION-MAKING.

In reality, decisions in a true democracy must be made collectively, through a general assembly of the people and not through its elected representatives.

The Assembly is such a form of general assembly of citizens.

The misuse of the word democracy has really devalued it.

In reality, power is corrupted by this elite, because its value system is not the one guided by morality, honor, dignity, conscience.

The current type of social system, social system, economic system constantly causes crises in every sphere of human activity.

The constantly created and deliberately provoked crises in international relations, politics, economics, education, healthcare are rooted in the main forms of market economy - personal interest and the constant pursuit of ever-increasing profits.

There is a system of organization and management of people's lives from the outside, and they cannot have any control and influence over those who govern their lives. This system is full of contradictions that provoke crises that are actually caused by the global Masonic mafia elite and its led and managed deep government and deep state. People's opinion is ignored, not taken into account, people's interests are violated, public goods are looted, and go to the management of private interests, under the pretext that man can not manage well state-owned companies, property, goods.

On the other hand, egoism, egocentrism, the pursuit of success at any cost and success that brings only profits, income, contribution of money, while ignoring the development of human creative and spiritual abilities, come to the fore.

Only such behavior and value system is tolerated, which leads to profits for certain individuals, companies, for certain interests, political elite, global Masonic mafia elite.

It turns out that a system of government with a high vertical structure and a hierarchical pyramid system of government increasingly ignores the interests of society and people, deletes them, replaces them with their own personal interests for profit.

On the other hand, the creative abilities of the person are suppressed, which does not necessarily bring profit, money, dividends and others.

Such abilities are rejected, ignored.

Apart from the fact that the hierarchical system of government, the vertical structure ceases to serve society and people, it at one point uses all kinds of coercive forms and measures against the people themselves.

"The forms of 'democracy' that we know so far, and which are based on the election of representatives to elect their representatives in power and in vertical hierarchical structures and organization, have nothing to do not only with direct democracy but also with democracy.

The elected representatives elect their representatives, and the control, accountability, responsibility, dependence of the respective representative of the representatives on the choice of the citizens is actually lost.

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This is an imaginary democracy.

An alternative to the current democracy is direct democracy.

They build institutions that ensure that every member of society can participate directly in decision-making at the political, economic, social, environmental, cultural and all levels.

Capitalism generates a consumer society whose value system is quite low, whose value system satisfies only the lowest human needs of Maslow's pyramid, where the most important are the ego, money, profit in money.

The direct democracy of the Theory of SOCIO-HUMANISM places man and the whole system in which man lives environment, ecological environment - planet, plants, animals, people at the center of this system.

The impact of these decisions on both the social system and the ecological system of the planet is always considered in decision-making.

In addition, the system of direct democracy of SOCIO-HUMANISM imposes on the one hand referendums on the choice of:

Program plan for a specific period. These plans-programs concern - public life, economy, social system, healthcare, education, internal and external security, external political and economic and international relations, the innovation system, the system of establishing state and / or state / private partnerships.

Need to change laws, create new laws.

Budgets for the implementation of these plans - programs for a specific period.

On a rotating basis, qualified personnel are selected by lot to implement and implement these plan-programs, and these qualified personnel have precisely defined for this position capacity, knowledge, experience, experience, achievements and others. As the choice of these shots is for a specific time. For this period of time, these frames are reported before the period during the period, at the end of the period and after the period.

These qualified staff have SHORT AND NON-RENEWABLE TERMS - the powers must be given for a short period. One-time and short terms.

EQUALITY - POLITICAL, SOCIAL, SOCIAL IS THE CORE OF DEMOCRACY AND ITS SINGLE CONDITION.

Because power corrupts, ie. those in office will not have the opportunity to corrupt themselves.

CONTROL of the implementation of these adopted plan programs in each area.

The control is from every citizen, constant access to the information about the plan-programs, their implementation.

CONTROL - before the term, during the term, at the end of the term, after the term.

CONTINUOUS ACCOUNTING

SANCTIONS - recall,

CONTROL LEVERS FOR RESPONSE TO

INSTITUTIONS OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY

The institutions are organized on a non-hierarchical basis.

The political, economic, social, ecological system are organized on the principle of self-government, control by citizens, accountability to citizens at any time, appropriate system of acceptance of these actions, sanction of actions that do not lead to the respective results, responsiveness of management staff.

THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

Election of the Chief Prosecutor, city, district prosecutors on the basis of referendums cover the relevant criteria and propose the relevant plan-programs

Control, reporting, t responsiveness

INSTITUTIONS OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY

All systems are an arrogant of the system of self-government, and control by civil society of accountability to civil society of the period, respectively a system of sanctions and recall.

On non-hierarchy

Direct democracy is applied in every sphere of the public, political, economic, ecological, social, cultural life of the citizens.

Equality of rights - half-sect equality

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An additional institution of political equality is the RIGHT TO FREE SPEECH.

In reality, the right to free speech enables every citizen to be a guardian of the public good, the public domain.

ie THE RIGHT TO TAKE THE WORD AND THE RIGHT TO SPEAK IS A BASIC PRINCIPLE IN DIRECT DEMOCRACY.

EVERYONE HAS THE RIGHT TO TAKE THE WORD AT ANY TIME, ON ANY ISSUE.

Everyone can talk.

Purity of democracy

It is also the right to tell the truth, to expose the lie, without having any consequences for the perpetrator.

This is the category - it makes citizens active, responsible for what they say, say. As well as the fact that these opinions expressed and others are important for the relevant institutions.

This helps citizens to be active in the whole process.

The possibility for citizens to be passive, whether out of fear, threats, or other racketeering, coercion, to tell the truth, must be destroyed.

Capitalism is just the opposite and opposite of democracy.

Under capitalism, there is a concentration of capital, human and natural resources in the hands of a small group of people, the so-called global Masonic mafia elite.

The real "democracy" at the moment is the one that belongs and serves the market of the owners of huge capitals, finances and others - the global Muscovite mafia elite - including Rothschild, Rockefeller, Morgan, Soros, Bull Gates and families of the black aristocracy and 13 families ruling the world-.

The capitalist system rests and survives only on this concentration of wealth, money and power.

All their companies have the power to do business that brings huge profits to them.

The lack of democracy also leads to the environmental problems and ecological crisis created by this global Masonic mafia elite.

ie in SOCIO-HUMANISM the main task is to cover the interests of man, of the ecological system, and of all its inhabitants, ENVIRONMENTAL SOLUTIONS CLIMATE CRISES AND SOLUTIONS require democracy.

SYSTEM OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY AND CONTROL OF THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

We have proved beyond doubt the mafia and corruption in the judiciary around the world. The oligarchy and the global Masonic mafia elite rule not only the states, their government, finances, capital, create all kinds of crises, we will not list them, but also the judiciary.

By mafiotizing the judiciary, this global mafiaized Masonic elite legitimizes theft of assets, capital, companies, repression, racketeering, theft, legalizing crimes committed by them.

The system of direct democracy and control of the judiciary in the Society created on the basis of the Theory of SOCIO-HUMANISM is the following:

1 /. With precise, clear criteria for experience, practice, experience, assessments, specializations when applying, junior judges are selected by respectively established citizens' councils on a rotating basis for a period of 2 / two / years, and the age cannot and should not be younger. for 30 years. To hold experience in law and legal sciences not less than 5-7 years. This is the election of junior judges at the district court level

2 /. The Citizens' Council exercises continuous control during this two-year period of court cases, acts, in connection with precisely defined ethical and moral and professional rules of conduct of junior judges. In case of violation - sanction - system of sanctions.

3 /. Citizens' councils are elected on a rotating basis by professional lawyers for a term of one year.

4 /. City and district judges are elected by referendum, based on a program presented to the respective candidate, who meets specific conditions - professional, internship, experience, and others. These judges are elected for a term of 2 / two / years. They have no immunity. Control of the actions by a civil commission elected on a rotating basis for 1 / one / year.

5 /. The heads of all courts are elected in referendums by the civil society from the respective district - city, district, in defense and presentation of a respective program by the candidate. Control of the actions of the respective head by a civil commission.

6 /. The heads of the supreme courts are elected by referendums from the entire population.

The heads of the courts of appeal shall be elected by referendum in the district concerned.

7 /. The chief prosecutor is elected by the entire population in a referendum, after presenting the horn.

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Control is carried out by the relevant civil law council, which is on a rotating basis for one year, and its members deal only with this at all times, have no right to advocate, provide services, consultations and more.

Prosecutors at the appropriate levels are elected on the same principles above.

SYSTEM OF DIRECT DEMOCRACY AND CONTROL OF THE LEGISLATIVE SYSTEM THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

1 /. Council on the agenda of changes to old laws, creation of new laws,

System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies.

There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates.

In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis from 2-3 years full time, paid, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice. others.

This is a body selected by lot to 150-200 people.

This council has and performs the role of setting the agenda, choosing areas, areas for legislation, changing laws in connection with a changed social environment and conditions.

2 /. Advice on areas of law - relevant type of law - example - administrative, criminal, civil law, property law, and others.

System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies.

There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates.

In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis from 2-3 years full time, paid, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice. others.

This is a body of 15 to 20 people selected by lot.

This council makes proposals for changing old laws, for drafting new laws depending on areas of legislation, changing laws in connection with a changed social environment and conditions.

3 /. Advice on proposals for changes in laws, for the creation of new laws, which include relevant experts, non-governmental organizations, for the coordination of relevant laws in connection with the laws, preparation of final proposals for laws, paragraphs, articles of laws.

System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies.

There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates.

In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis from 2-3 years full time, paid, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice. others.

This is a body selected by lot to 150-200 people.

This council has and performs the role of setting the agenda, choosing areas, areas for legislation, changing laws in connection with a changed social environment and conditions.

4 /. COUNCIL - jury for voting on the relevant laws.

System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies.

There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates.

In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis from 2-3 years full time, paid, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice. others.

This is a body selected by lot to 150-200 people.

This council has and performs the role of setting the agenda, choosing areas, areas for legislation, changing laws in connection with a changed social environment and conditions.

5 /. Council for control of the legislative process, control of application of laws, implementation of laws, consideration of complaints and others.

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System of selection by lot of applicants - professionals - lawyers to participate in law enforcement agencies.

There are respectively developed criteria, requirements, minimum criteria and data requirements - in terms of experience, qualifications, expertise, which must be met by the candidates.

In reality, the drawing of lots is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis from 2-3 years full time, paid, without the right to perform other activities.

In reality, the draw is based on a list of volunteers who have met these requirements and who will work on a rotating basis from 2-3 years full time, paid, without the right to perform other activities - to be lawyers, to give advice. others.

This is a body selected by lot to 150-200 people.

This council has and performs the role of setting the agenda, choosing areas, areas for legislation, changing laws in connection with a changed social environment and conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

In this article we have shown the main reasons for the society created on the basis of the Theory of Socio-Humanism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobрева, developed in 2006. , the system of direct democracy in the legislative, judicial and executive branches.

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